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Early wood quality assessment for a better use of the forest resource. The DigiMedFor project

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Abstract. The in-situ wood evaluation aims to advance timber quality assessment by addressing it earlier in the supply chain, directly in the forest on standing trees and shortly after harvest on felled logs. This perspective provides forest owners with valuable insights into the quality of their properties, offering a clear understanding of the potential value of their trees. Unlike traditional methods, our approach is designed to provide quick and easy-to-use evaluations, saving time and effort while delivering enhanced value information.

An inventory app is being trained to assess the stems of standing trees, generating a quality index that will be included in the inventory report for each forest parcel. Both forest owners and users will benefit from this enhanced understanding of forest compartment quality, enabling more efficient buying and selling decisions.

Keywords: stem quality, mobile app, forest inventory.

1 Introduction

Along the forest-wood value chain, wood quality is often assessed on the semi-finished or finished product stage, when both marketing strategies or compliance with the legislation (i.e. in the construction sector) make it either profitable or necessary. However, anticipating the quality evaluation to forests stands or roundwood soon after logging could provide additional advantages from both a forest management and resource exploitation perspective [1]. On the one hand, having information about quality besides quantity could support decision-makers in silvicultural choices to cultivate value. On the other hand, a better understanding of the wood resource would optimize selling and purchasing decisions, finding the best destination for the material according to its qualitative characteristics.

In this context, the DigiMedFor project aims to modernise the technological landscape of the Mediterranean forest-wood supply chain (<https://digimedfor.eu/>). The project focuses on simultaneously enhancing competitiveness and promoting sustainable management by, among other initiatives, implementing quick and easy-to-use tools for

assessing the quality of standing trees and logs. Here, the activities done to evaluate standing trees are presented.

2 Material and methods

The quality assessment is using an inventory mobile application, Trestima, to assign to each forest unit a quality index related to the quality of the trees inside it.

Trestima is a mobile application working on pictures taken from the mobile camera while walking across the forest [2]. Thanks to image analysis techniques, tree stems are segmented, the wooden species are identified and their stem diameters are measured (Figure 1). Reports about the basal area, diameter distribution, tree height and volume are produced.

Fig. 1. Image analyzed by Trestima app for tree recognition and diameter measurement. Pictures were taken in Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii*) stand of the Vallombrosa Forest (Tuscany, Italy)

In the territory of the Model Forest of Montagne Fiorentina, Italy, a survey was done to evaluate the quality of Douglas fir tree stems in 31 forest units. A quality index was elaborated so to divide the plot into three classes: being the class 1 the best and the three the worst. The index was based mainly on the first 5-6 m stem form and branchiness. A quality index was assigned to each surveyed plot.

Pictures were taken with the mobile app in all the plots, and a training was carried out to improve stem segmentation and branch recognition, and subsequently predict the quality index of the plot.

3 Results

The smart application was effective in segmenting stems and defining them accordingly. However, further refinement is required for branchiness, as the segmentation was not sufficiently accurate for longer branches (see Figure 2). Nonetheless, the correlation

between the Human-made quality index and the Trestima QI prediction was moderately significant ($r = 0.58$). Efforts are currently underway to enhance the detection of protruding branches, which is expected to significantly improve the picture-based quality predictions.

Fig. 2. Stem and branches segmentation.

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References

1. Nocetti, M.; Brunetti, M.: Advancements in wood quality assessment: standing tree visual evaluation—a review. *Forests*, 15, 943, (2024).
2. Ficko, A. Bayesian evaluation of smartphone applications for forest inventories in small forest holdings. *Forests*, 11, 1148, (2020).

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